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Time to Act: Strengthening Edinburgh's Support for African-Led Enterprises

Dr Bekee Bariture, Associate Lecturer of Management, University of the West of Scotland, UK.

Dr Kingsley Obi Omeihe, Senior Lecturer of Marketing and Entrepreneurship, University of the West of Scotland, UK. Chair of Entrepreneurship in Minority Groups Special Interest Group.

Dr Ibiyemi Omeihe, Lecturer of Enterprise, University of the West of Scotland, UK. Chair of African Entrepreneurship Community of Interest.

Dr Ijeoma Okpanum, Lecturer of Management, University of Aberdeen, UK. Chair of Organisational Behaviour, Academy for African Studies.

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Executive summary

This policy note explores the challenges faced by African entrepreneurs based in Edinburgh, Scotland. We examine how structural disadvantages in access to finance, networks and mentorship constrain key aspects of starting, sustaining and growing a business. These constraints demand new approaches to supporting minority entrepreneurs and raise important questions for local economic development and inclusive policymaking. While African entrepreneurs contribute significantly to the city's economy and society, persistent inequalities continue to affect their progress. We propose a policy agenda that draws attention to these barriers and their longer-term effects, particularly for underrepresented business owners who face exclusion in an increasingly competitive environment.

Why African entrepreneurs in Edinburgh need more than recognition?

Without more tailored and effective interventions, Scotland risks missing out on the full potential these businesses offer. This calls for closer attention from all relevant stakeholders across the ecosystem. We argue that the lived experiences of many of these entrepreneurs warrant closer scrutiny and a more nuanced understanding. This is particularly important because much of the existing research has overlooked their resilience, adaptability, and the significant contributions

they make to Edinburgh's diverse economy. Indeed, much of what is currently known about African entrepreneurship derives from studies that adopt a more detached perspective. At the policy level, progress has also been slow. To date, efforts have primarily focused on improving access to finance and assessing potential growth impacts for entrepreneurs. This is why this policy paper aims to accelerate progress for African entrepreneurs, where we believe further action is clearly needed.

Building on the access to finance report led by Adeoti *et al.*, (2024), we offer policy suggestions that highlight where more support is needed. We recognise that real change won't happen overnight or in isolation, it needs to be part of a wider policy framework that connects these entrepreneurs' activities with Scotland's broader industrial strategy. Taking a broader approach, we explore how policy decisions can affect different aspects of African entrepreneurship. We ask how new policy frameworks can encourage growth and development for African entrepreneurs and support the wider entrepreneurial context.

Background

Edinburgh's business community is changing, and immigrant entrepreneurs are at the heart of that transformation. In recent years, businesses led by immigrants have become an increasingly visible force, shaping not only the city's economy but also its cultural and social fabric (Omeihe, 2024; Bekee, 2025). Their impact is more than anecdotal: this is because immigrant-led SMEs contribute over £13 billion in annual revenue and support upwards of 107,000 jobs across Scotland (FSB Report, 2020; Bekee and Omeihe, 2022). Among these, African entrepreneurs represent a growing share. Their businesses are generating employment, attracting local investment and anchoring communities. Their presence has prompted overdue discussions, not just about how to extend support, but about whether the wider ecosystem is fit for purpose.

While previous research and policy reports have focused on entrepreneurship across the UK (Brynin *et al.*, 2019; Esper *et al.*, 2020; Vershinina and Rodgers, 2020) there remains a need to understand how African entrepreneurs respond to these challenges within their specific contexts, including those aspiring to start new ventures (Amoako, 2019; Omeihe and Omeihe, 2021; Falehin *et al.*, 2024; Bekee, 2025). Unfortunately, many still face familiar obstacles: limited access to finance, narrow market pathways, and underdeveloped networks. For all the progress, there is a sense that existing support structures, however well-meaning, have not kept pace with the ambition or potential of those they are meant to serve.

Discussion points

We now discuss the interpretation of our findings. Here, we present detailed qualitative evidence originating from two complementary but sophisticated sources. Our first source was derived from a set of interviews and intensive dialogues with 33 African entrepreneurs conducted in the summer of 2024. This was further reinforced with observations, documentary evidence and case studies as multiple sources of evidence (Yin, 2014; Omeihe and Harrison, 2024). This allowed for the empirical inquiry of unclear boundaries between context and the phenomenon being studied.

To sum up, several of our findings are worth highlighting:

Firstly, while our study builds on previous research into minority entrepreneurship (Carter et al., 2015; Vershinina and Rodgers, 2020; Falehin et al., 2024), we go further by uncovering how African entrepreneurs in Scotland have been largely overlooked. Our work addresses this gap and aligns with the Scottish Funding Council's priority to bridge the divide between research, policy, and practice. We show that African entrepreneurs, both across Scotland and more widely in the UK, continue to make valuable contributions to the economy, well beyond their immediate communities. However, with this progress comes renewed attention to the social and economic barriers many still face. These challenges deserve greater recognition and action. Our research helps to address this by focusing on the potential economic benefits that could result from better understanding and responding to these barriers.

Secondly, while we highlight the positive impact of these entrepreneurs, our study also reveals the critical role that social networks play. These connections often help African entrepreneurs access capital and identify new opportunities. Many still rely on informal funding sources, such as family, friends, and community groups, because traditional bank loans remain difficult to access. High repayment costs, weak credit histories and limited support in developing strong business plans mean many turn to alternative ways of financing their ventures.

Thirdly, we found strong evidence supporting the role of trade associations and community networks. This was a consistent theme across our interviews. Cultural and religious associations played a proactive role in helping entrepreneurs find new opportunities and overcome competitive markets. These groups also provided practical support, in sharing valuable information and offering referrals that helped drive business growth. Our findings echo previous research on how social networks shape the success of minority-owned businesses (Ram et al., 2021; Carter et al., 2015; Vershinina and Rodgers, 2020; Jones et al, 2022).

Lastly, our research identified several regulatory challenges that limit growth for African entrepreneurs. These included issues with licensing, compliance and access to business support services. In addition, while some participants mentioned experiences of exclusion and racial discrimination, these were not the main concerns raised. Instead, many were more focused on structural issues, such as the imbalance between supply and demand in highly competitive, low-barrier markets where many operate. These findings suggest a need for more targeted policy, tailored support, better access to finance, and inclusive policies, which are essential if we are to unlock the full potential of this growing and dynamic part of the economy.

Main Takeaways for Key Stakeholders: African Entrepreneurs in Scotland

- African entrepreneurs in Scotland make a growing and meaningful contribution to the Scottish and UK economies yet remain under-researched and underserved in policy and practice.
- This group continues to operate beyond their immediate communities, creating jobs and driving business activity, but still faces significant social and economic barriers.

- There is a need for policymakers, researchers, and practitioners to better align efforts and close the gap between academic research, policy development, and real-world support.
- Social and community networks, especially cultural, religious, and trade associations, play a key role in helping African entrepreneurs access capital, information and market opportunities.
- Many African entrepreneurs still rely on informal sources of finance due to barriers in accessing formal banking services. These include high loan costs, poor credit access, and limited support for business planning.
- Regulatory challenges, such as licensing and compliance requirements, often hinder business growth and create added burdens for small, minority-owned enterprises.
- While some respondents mentioned exclusion and discrimination, most were concerned with structural and market-related issues, particularly competition in low-entry, low-margin sectors.
- Policy efforts must go beyond one-size-fits-all approaches and provide tailored support that addresses the specific needs of African entrepreneurs and other underrepresented business groups.
- Stronger cross-sector collaboration, between government, business support services, academia, and community networks, is essential to unlock the full potential of this entrepreneurial group.

Building on these insights, we propose a clear and actionable framework to bring together policymakers, community organisations, and business support services. This framework is designed to tackle the specific challenges African entrepreneurs in Scotland face by encouraging targeted support and ensuring that policies are not only relevant but truly responsive to their needs.

Figure 1: Framework for Supporting African Entrepreneurs

Policy and practice recommendations

This study's findings have real relevance to policymakers interested in entrepreneurship within the UK and particularly Scotland. Across policy circles, issues around access to finance continue to gain ground. We want to push this further by emphasising that limited access to financing is one of the biggest obstacles preventing African entrepreneurs in Edinburgh from being successful. However, to date, policy reports and decision makers have not explicitly devoted attention to this issue.

In terms of policy recommendations, it is evident from this research that financial institutions frequently display bias, whether intentional or inadvertent, which increases the likelihood that loan applications from minority business owners will be denied. Rather than taking a broad approach, we believe that new policies should focus on launching targeted financial initiatives to address this problem. Related to this is the need for grants, low interest loans, and microfinance options specifically designed for African minority entrepreneurs. Mentorship programmes that pair these business owners with knowledgeable advisors can help them craft strong business plans and improve their chances of securing funding. Similarly, we recommend the establishment of business accelerators and incubators that specialise in serving minority enterprises. We say this because these would provide African business owners with access to potential partners, investors and clients.

Our primary concern is that one of the biggest challenges facing African minority entrepreneurs is systemic prejudice. Biased hiring practices, unfair treatment in the workplace, and exclusion from business opportunities are just some of the ways this discrimination manifests and must

be addressed. The approach we take is informed by our findings. We recommend implementing anti-discrimination laws and practices across the public and private sectors. On the face of it, launching awareness raising initiatives can also help shift public perceptions. Additionally, the formation of advisory boards comprising executives from minority businesses can ensure that African entrepreneurs' perspectives are represented in the policy making process, towards more responsive and effective outcomes.

The key point here is that supporting African minority businesses requires the creation and implementation of inclusive policy frameworks. Beyond this, minority business associations can work collaboratively with local and national governments to identify the unique challenges these business owners face. To conclude, we believe that through such collaborations, policies offering tailored support, such as tax breaks, streamlined regulatory procedures, and improved access to business development services, can be developed.

Takeaway Recommendations: African Entrepreneurs in Scotland

To support African entrepreneurs in Edinburgh, we need to move beyond broad promises and focus on real, practical action. Their challenges are specific and their contributions are valuable. Change will come through better access to finance, fairer treatment, stronger networks and policies shaped with the community, not just for it. The recommendations below offer a clear path forward.

- **Targeted financial programmes.** Develop and implement grants, low-interest loans, and microfinance schemes specifically designed to meet the unique needs of African entrepreneurs. Simplify application processes to encourage uptake and reduce barriers.
- **Bias audits in lending.** Require financial institutions to conduct regular independent audits of their lending practices to identify and eliminate bias, whether intentional or inadvertent, that contributes to higher loan rejection rates for minority business owners. Introduce accountability frameworks to ensure fair treatment.
- **Business accelerators and mentorship.** Invest in the creation and expansion of business accelerators and incubators dedicated to minority entrepreneurs, alongside mentorship schemes that connect African business owners with experienced advisors. These programmes should focus on improving business planning, networking, and access to investment.
- **Anti-discrimination enforcement.** Enhance enforcement of existing anti-discrimination laws across public and private sectors, especially regarding hiring, workplace treatment, and access to economic opportunities. Complement this with public awareness campaigns to challenge stereotypes and foster inclusive business environments.
- **Collaborative policy design.** Establish ongoing partnerships between policymakers and African business associations to co-design responsive and tailored entrepreneurship policies. This collaboration should help bridge the gap between policy intentions and real challenges faced on the ground.
- **Advisory boards for minority voices.** Form advisory boards composed of African and other minority business leaders to provide direct input into the development,

implementation and review of entrepreneurship policies. This ensures minority perspectives effectively shape decision-making and policy outcomes.

As with any study, ours has its own set of limitations, particularly regarding the number of respondents. To develop a more robust research agenda, it would be valuable to gain insights from a larger empirical dataset. Nevertheless, in light of our findings, we believe that the issues identified in this study are both timely and relevant and could be further explored through comparisons across different ethnic blocs.

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